

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF $\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Band	g_{11}	g_1	G
X	2.230	2.083	2.77
Q	2.235(A)	2.074(A)	
	2.105(B)	2.075(B)	

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Polarographic Study of Complexation Behaviour of β -Resorcyaldehyde with some Transition Metal Cations in Aqueous Ethanol (70%) Media

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β -Resorcyaldehyde as a bidentate ligand is of special interest because of its use in the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions¹. Potentiometric studies² on complex formation of this ligand with Mn^{II} ,

Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} revealed stepwise formation of complexes. In the present study, polarographic examination of complexation of β -resorcyaldehyde with these cations has been carried out and stabilities of the complexes have been determined by Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method³⁻⁵.

Experimental

A Polariter PO4g Radiometer polarograph at a chart speed of 2 cm min^{-1} using a Sargent capillary with characteristics $m=1.068 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=4.3 \text{ s}$ for 70 cm mercury head at constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$) was used to record the polarograms. Nitrogen gas was bubbled to deaerate the solutions taken in a double-walled H-type cell with a built-in SCE in the second limb of the cell. pH was measured on an ELICO-LI-120 digital pH meter ($\pm 0.01 \text{ pH unit}$).

β -Resorcyaldehyde (m.p. 135–36°) (Bio-organics, India) was used. The metal perchlorates were prepared from the respective oxides, hydroxides, carbonates or nitrates. The ligand solution (1.0 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared in aldehyde-free ethanol.

Test solutions contained (a) metal ion (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), ethanol (7.0 ml), gelatin (0.25 ml; 0.2%), made up to 10 ml with double-distilled water and (b) metal ion (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), gelatin (0.25 ml, 0.2%), increasing volumes of ligand in ethanol, additional ethanol to make up to 7 ml and water to make up to 10 ml, after adjusting pH with perchloric acid or lithium hydroxide, as required.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic characteristic data are presented in Table 1. The polarograms are all well-defined diffusion-controlled cathodic waves with slopes 45, 50, 55 and 60 mV for the respective metal-ligand systems

The decrease in diffusion currents ($\Delta \bar{i}_d$) is plotted against $\log [L]$ and the sigmoidal pseudo-formation curve was integrated according to Fronaeus⁶ to provide $F'_0[L]$ data at each ligand concentration. These values are then plotted

TABLE 1—COMPLEXATION OF M(II) IONS WITH β -RESORCYALDEHYDE IN 70% (ETHANOL-WATER) MEDIA AT pH's 6.55, 7.77, 6.92, 4.87 AND 8.71 RESPECTIVELY

$m=1.068 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=4.3 \text{ s}$, $h=70 \text{ cm}$, $\text{temp.}=298 \text{ K}$

[L] mol dm^{-3}	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Mn})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Mn})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Co})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Co})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Ni})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Ni})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Cu})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Cu})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Zn})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Zn})$ μ_A
0.00000	1.32	3.29	1.33	1.19	1.10	1.58	0.02	3.89	1.20	2.77
0.00001	1.33	3.28	1.34	0.93	1.11	1.33	0.03	3.59	1.21	2.45
0.00005	1.34	3.26	1.36	0.89	1.12	1.32	0.05	3.55	1.22	2.43
0.0001	1.36	3.23	1.37	0.87	1.14	1.30	0.07	3.53	1.23	2.41
0.0005	1.38	3.19	1.38	0.83	1.16	1.26	0.08	3.49	1.24	2.37
0.0010	1.40	3.17	1.40	0.79	1.18	1.24	0.09	3.47	1.26	2.35
0.0020	1.42	3.15	1.42	0.75	1.19	1.22	0.10	3.45	1.28	2.31
0.0050	1.43	3.11	1.44	0.73	1.21	1.18	0.12	3.43	1.30	2.23

$\log \beta_2(\text{Mn})=6.78$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Co})=8.07$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Ni})=8.60$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Cu})=9.23$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Zn})=7.79$.

against $\log [L]$ and limiting slopes of the curves yield (N_{\max}/k) values. From the knowledge of the maximum coordination number, N_{\max} for each metal ion, the k value is calculated. Multiplying $\log F_0[L]$ values by the k values, yields $\log F_0[L]$ values. The $F_0[L]$ vs $[L]$ plots then give the values of formation constants^{2,3,5,7,8}.

The polarographic studies have been carried out at three temperatures, 288, 298 and 308 K and the stability constants are calculated along with thermodynamic parameters^{9,10} (Table 2).

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH β -RESORCYLALDEHYDE

Metal ion	T K	$\log \beta_2$	$-\Delta G$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
MnII	288	7.05 ± 0.01	38.92	46.87	-27.26
	298	6.78 ± 0.01	38.75		
	308	6.77 ± 0.01	38.74		
CoII	288	8.35 ± 0.01	46.05	55.52	-31.79
	298	8.06 ± 0.01	46.04		
	308	7.77 ± 0.02	45.82		
NiII	288	8.64 ± 0.04	49.61	71.62	-75.72
	298	8.60 ± 0.03	49.06		
	308	8.26 ± 0.01	48.65		
CuII	288	9.56 ± 0.01	52.88	61.27	-31.33
	298	9.23 ± 0.02	52.83		
	308	9.21 ± 0.01	52.78		
ZnII	288	7.75 ± 0.04	43.07	48.76	-19.13
	289	7.79 ± 0.03	43.06		
	308	7.29 ± 0.03	43.05		

The order of overall stabilities ($\log \beta_2$) at 298 K have been found to be $Mn^{2+} < Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ ^{11,12}. The negative values of entropy for all the complexes indicate higher order in the complex molecules.

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Kinetic Study of Oxidation of Salicylidene *o*-Aminobenzoic Acid and Salicylidene *o*-Aminobenzothiol by Cerium(IV) in Acidic Medium

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A survey of literature has shows that much work has been done on the oxidation of various organic compounds by Ce^{IV} in acidic medium^{1,2}. Kinetics of oxidation of mandelic, *dl*-malic and lactic acid³, isobutyric acid⁴ and dicarboxylic acids⁵ by cerium(IV) have been studied by various workers. The present communication reports the kinetic study of the oxidations of Schiff base salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol by Ce^{IV} in acidic medium which has not been studied so far.

Experimental

The kinetic runs were initiated by adding a temperature-equilibrated solution of Schiff base to a reaction vessel (at 40.0°) containing the required amount of sulphuric acid respectively, cerium(IV) sulphate solution and double-distilled water. The course of reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquot (5 ml) at different time intervals and determining the unreacted cerium(IV) by ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ce^{IV} and these two Schiff bases was studied by the method described elsewhere². The equivalents of cerium(IV) used per mole of salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol were found to be eight at 40° in both the cases.

Results and Discussion

The reaction has been found to obey first order reaction in $[Ce^{IV}]$ as straight lines were obtained by plotting $\log [Ce^{IV}]$ vs time for each Schiff base, and pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the slopes of these lines. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k) were directly proportional to the concentration of Schiff base. This fact is confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs $1/[Schiff\ base]$. These plots were straight lines having an intercept on $1/k$. These facts show complex formation between Ce^{IV} and the substrates, which subsequently decomposed to the products in the rate-determining step. The reaction velocity was found to decrease with the increasing concentration of sulphuric acid.

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